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BEFORE FRIEDRICH (FRITZ) BALTHES. THE NINETEENTH-CENTURY ARCHITECTURE OF THE FORMER EVANGELICAL SCHOOL IN GHERDEAL

ILEANA BURNICHIOIU*

Abstract: At the eastern edge of Sibiu County lies a small village of medieval origin Gherdeal (well known in today's media), whose Evangelical Saxon elementary school was among those redesigned by the architect Fritz Balthes (1882–1914). This occurred in 1912, and the following year, the school was converted into a multifunctional building intended to meet several needs of the local community. These aspects are already largely familiar, as Balthes's work has, over the past decade, attracted increasing interest, materialised in projects and studies dedicated both to understanding the diversity of his oeuvre and to safeguarding the artistic heritage he generated.

The present study turns its attention to the earlier phases and subsequent transformations of the school's architecture before Balthes intervened in Gherdeal, tracing its history up to the present day. The analysis draws upon present field data, both new (2023–2024) and archival surveys of the building (produced by three different authors), as well as dendrochronological investigations. In this way, the older nucleus of the school – dating to the mid-nineteenth century – is reassessed. This earlier construction was based on drawings signed by Mathias Joseph Angermann (1808–1880), an engineer and former imperial official of the Cincu Seat, whose professional activity was varied yet remains almost unknown; here, we provide a few initial reference points. In the history of the Gherdeal school, the “Angermann” phase was followed by an attempt at adaptation and enlargement in 1905 (never realised), and only thereafter by the “Balthes” phase. The case examined represents a distinct example of Transylvania's historical educational architecture, which has attracted insufficient attention in terms of in-depth study and preservation, despite occasionally being included in the *List of Historical Monuments*.

Keywords: Transylvania, elementary schools, Saxon village architecture, community architecture, Mathias Joseph Angermann

Rezumat: La limita estică a județului Sibiu, există un mic sat cu origini medievale, Gherdeal (bine cunoscut în mass-media de astăzi), a cărui școală primară a sașilor evanghelici a fost re-proiectată de arhitectul Fritz Balthes (1882–1914). Acest lucru s-a petrecut în 1912. Anul următor, școala a fost transformată într-o clădire multifuncțională, menită să răspundă mai multor nevoi ale comunității locale. Toate acestea sunt deja în bună măsură cunoscute, activitatea lui Balthes bucurându-se în ultimul deceniu de un interes sporit, concretizat în proiecte și studii dedicate atât înțelegerii diversității operei sale, cât și protejării patrimoniului artistic pe care l-a generat. De aceea, lucrarea de față vizează vechimea și transformările prin care a trecut arhitectura școlii anterioare lui Balthes la Gherdeal, până în zilele noastre, creionate cu ajutorul datelor actuale din teren, al releveelor noi (2023–2024) și vechi ale clădirii (cu trei autori diferiți), dar și cu ajutorul unor analize dendrocronologice. În acest mod, este datat nucleul mai vechi al școlii, de la mijlocul secolului al XIX-lea. Acesta s-a construit pe baza unor desene semnate de Mathias Joseph Angermann (1808–1880), inginer și fost funcționar imperial în Scaunul Cincu, cu o activitate diversă, dar aproape necunoscută,

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pentru care oferim aici câteva repere de început. În istoria școlii din Gherdeal, etapa „Angermann” a fost urmată de o tentativă de adaptare și extindere încă din anul 1905 (nepușă în practică), și abia apoi de etapa „Balthes”. Cazul analizat este un exemplu aparte dintr-o arhitectură istorică a educației din Transilvania față de care nu există suficient interes pentru cunoaștere aprofundată și pentru prezervare, chiar dacă se regăsește uneori în *Lista Monumentelor Istorice*.

Cuvinte cheie: Transilvania, școli elementare, arhitectură rurală săsească, arhitectură comunitară, Mathias Joseph Angermann

Introduction

Gherdeal (German: Gürteln; Hungarian: Gerdály) is a small village of medieval origin located along the eastern edge of Sibiu County in a remote and difficult-to-access area within the commune of Bruuiu (southern Transylvania). Throughout the twentieth century, the settlement experienced a demographic decline from which it has yet to recover.¹ This decline has had significant adverse consequences for the local architecture – ecclesiastical, residential, and defensive – as well as for local folk art.² This study focuses on the architecture of the former Evangelical elementary school in the village – a case that, despite being highly vulnerable from a conservation perspective, has been largely neglected by the literature.³

Published information on the architecture of the Gherdeal school has so far been limited and largely unilateral, relying on archival sources (both visual and textual) concerning the period of 1912–1913, when architect Friedrich (Fritz) Balthes (1882–1914) transformed the building into a multifunctional facility designed to meet several needs of the local Evangelical community.⁴ This architect, who also played a distinctive cultural role in southern Transylvania, remained forgotten for a long time.⁵ However, approaching the centenary of his death, a broad group of scholars began studying his archive – including original architectural surveys – to document his built heritage (which had fallen into disrepair as the Saxons emigrated from Transylvania) and attempt to have representative buildings of his included in Romania’s *List of Historical Monuments* (LHM).⁶ Between

¹ Abandonment and isolation have transformed Gherdeal into one of the most publicised villages. In 2017, it counted only seven inhabitants – four Romanians and three Saxons (Rudolf 2021, 156). Following a series of property transactions, the houses now all have owners, though most reside in the village only temporarily, either during holidays or while carrying out renovations.

² It is not only the architecture – namely the monument churches of both the Saxons and the Orthodox Romanians (St. Nicholas, pre-1800), the Evangelical parish house, and the dwellings in general – that deserves attention, but also the Saxon folk art, already promoted by E. Antoni (Antoni 1935, 217–224).

³ In fact, no historiography of school architecture in rural Saxon communities exists for Transylvania (such as can be found in other cultural contexts), and their protection – even for those included in Romania’s *List of Historical Monuments* (LHM) – remains largely formal. An exception, prior to the schools of Balthes among the Saxons, may be considered the “Latin School” in the commune of Cincu (Brașov County), published by Minghiat, Lucescu, and Pop (2001–2003, 65–75), although it has not benefited from a thorough, multidisciplinary investigation. Otherwise, many examples face a sad fate, even when included in the LHM: the school in Bruuiu is up for sale; that in Cincșor (Brașov County) was converted in 2014 and remains unlisted; while the one in Cața (1884) (Brașov County) has undergone improper interventions etc.

⁴ Bucur, Balthes [2016]; Rudolf 2021; Foth 2022a.

⁵ This formed part of a broader project, as detailed by the editors of the 2021 volume (Rudolf, Fabini 2021, 3–5).

⁶ Rudolf 2021, 156–159.

2014 and 2022, Balthes's work was the subject of exhibitions, lectures, articles, brochures, catalogues, and a volume of studies featuring the rural elementary schools he designed in the villages of Cincșor (1909–1911),⁷ Bruuiu (1911–1912), Gherdeal (1912), and Veseud (1913–1914). For Gherdeal specifically, notable references include Gerhild Rudolf's article, the documentation of architect Ioan Bucur (in collaboration with the MONUMENTUM Association and Hermann Balthes for LHM listing and promotion),⁸ and Gyöngyvér Foth's doctoral thesis,⁹ which analysed Balthes's architectural work within the broader framework of Saxon contributions to early twentieth-century Transylvanian architecture and the development of a national style among Transylvanian Saxons in relation to the German architectural movement. Across all of these works, the presence of a school in Gherdeal before that designed by Balthes could only be approximated to the seventeenth or eighteenth century.¹⁰ At that time, the building was abandoned, with several components in ruin (e.g., stair access, roof, interior walls, ceiling), and the prospects for detailed field research were nonexistent. This approximate dating was formalised when the building was officially added to the LHM in 2017.¹¹

Since 1990, the Gherdeal school building has undergone multiple phases: abandonment and destruction of its architectural components and finishes; restitution; sale; listing; and emergency intervention (2018–2020).¹² On several occasions prior to 2020, interventions were limited to the removal of debris, the dismantling of elements at risk of collapse (including a small bell tower on the roof), repairs to degraded masonry, and the implementation of wooden reinforcements and temporary roofing (Pl. I). However, only after 2022 did specialised studies commence; soon after, in 2023–2024, the development of a new architectural project for the revitalisation of the site became possible.¹³ On this occasion, available archival data – both published and unpublished, visual and written – were critically correlated with dendrochronological analyses (B. Tóth, Anno Domini Dendrolab, Miercurea Ciuc, 2024) and new non-invasive surveys of the elevations (I. Burnichioiu, L. Kiss) and foundations (L. Barna).¹⁴

This article outlines the local context in which the monument emerged, presents the current academic field surrounding this case, and highlights the results of recent research conducted in 2023–2024, placing a particular emphasis on the pre-Balthes school architecture.

⁷ In Cincșor, Balthes also took over an older school building to extend it. I would like to thank Radu Bărlă for several suggestions concerning this case and the photographer J. H. Briegel referred to in this paper.

⁸ Bucur, Balthes [2016], 26–28.

⁹ Foth 2022a, 163–165; see also Foth 2022b.

¹⁰ An exception is Fabini (1998, I, 257), which mentions the construction of a school in the mid-nineteenth century.

¹¹ Costiuc 2017, 93. The designation under which it was listed – “Evangelical Elementary School” – is conventional and does not encompass all the functions the building once had (SB-II-m-B-21135).

¹² The building is currently owned by the ANIMA VIVA Foundation, represented by Atena Iliescu.

¹³ *Consolidarea, restaurarea și punerea în valoare a fostei Școli elementare evanghelice din Gherdeal, com. Bruuiu, jud. Sibiu* (“Consolidation, restoration, and valorization of the former Evangelical Elementary School in Gherdeal, Bruuiu Commune, Sibiu County”), carried out by the MODUL 28 architecture office in Sibiu and supported by the National Heritage Institute (NHI).

¹⁴ See the Bibliography list.

Historical context of the local area

Reliable attestations of medieval settlement in Gherdeal may be traced as far back as the third decade of the fourteenth century (*Valle Gertrudis, Gyrtlen*), although they are sparse and limited in content. They primarily document conflicts between Saxon inhabitants and neighbouring villages, the village's affiliation with the Cincu Seat, and losses incurred due to fires, natural disasters, or invasions (by Turks, Tatars, and Kuruc forces).¹⁵ At the centre of the village, which is dispersed along several valleys, a fortified church stands on slightly elevated ground with enclosing walls and flanking towers, though its origins and subsequent transformations have yet to be fully understood.

Prior research on external attacks has largely supported the hypothesis that the fortification occurred in line with those in nearby villages,¹⁶ namely sometime between the second half of the fifteenth century and early in the sixteenth century. From then onward, some documents record donations (in cash and building materials) or tax exemptions granted by the Sibiu Province to Gherdeal.¹⁷ In 1520, the village received funds for completing the fortifications. A few years later, in 1532, sources indicate that the village comprised just fourteen taxable households, making it one of the smallest in the area.¹⁸

This modest settlement pattern is also reflected in the Josephinian survey (1769–1773) (Pl. II/1), although a group of Romanians joined the Saxon population after 1700.¹⁹ In the subsequent survey (1869–1887, 1:25,000), two churches are represented: the Saxon church near the approximate village centre (Pl. II/2), accompanied by a building to the northwest that's presumed to have been the school, and the Romanian church at the far southwest end of the village. The number of houses in the village appears to have increased, as confirmed by written sources, which recorded ninety-five and ninety-nine houses in 1882 and 1891, respectively. In 1869, Gherdeal (Târnava Mare County) had 444 inhabitants; however, the population soon began to decline, falling to 354 by 1910.

Former elementary school in Gherdeal: current state of preservation

The monument is located at the centre of the settlement, at the northwest edge of the plot occupied by the fortified church, facing the road that leads into the village. Incomplete joinery, deteriorated plaster, and a roof covered with a temporary sheathing give the building today an even more desolate appearance than in 2014–2016 (Pl. I/2–4).

Although prior research has not delineated different construction phases on published plans or undertaken any detailed analysis, earlier research has already indicated that the building consists of an older core – the evangelical elementary school – that Fritz Balthes extended northwards with a ground floor reserved for the community and an upper floor

¹⁵ On theories of colonisation and the evolution of the medieval village, see Nægler (1981, 76); Nussbächer, Klima (1985, 4); Fabini (1998, 257). Regarding the various historical name variants – initially connected with St Gertrud, later evolving in the Middle Ages into forms such as *Gyrtlen* and then *Gürtlen* (“belt”) – see Suciu (1967, I, s.v. Gherdeal) and Szabó (2003, s.v. Gherdeal).

¹⁶ For example, Ruja, Stejărișu, Netuș, Noiștat, Brădeni, and Iacobeni.

¹⁷ Gheorghiu 1985. In the LHM: sixteenth–nineteenth centuries.

¹⁸ Fabini 1998, 257.

¹⁹ Information on the Romanian population of the eighteenth–nineteenth centuries and on the Orthodox church has been synthesized by Abrudan 2023, 29–55.

dedicated to the school.²⁰ Consequently, the two wings differ in volume, height and façade treatment: the southern wing is lower, with a slightly recessed façade and an approximately north–south roof ridge orientation, while the northern wing is developed vertically, with the roof ridge oriented east–west. The site topography causes the eastern part of the building to be almost entirely embedded at ground-floor level (Pl. I/3–4). In what follows, the two wings will be detailed with field data, which, together with archival sources, will aid in more precisely determining the building’s phases of construction and spatial adaptation.

Southern wing

The southern wing rises on an approximately rectangular plan measuring ca. 12.50 × 9.45 m externally, comprising a double tract. The perimeter walls are approximately 0.65 m thick at the ground-floor level and 0.50 m thick at the upper-floor level. The main façade has two opening axes due to the recovery of a previously walled-up opening during recent interventions (Pl. I/2–3); these openings differ in size, with areas of degraded or intentionally removed plaster revealing the original stratigraphy.

The southern façade, also with two opening axes, serves as the access façade, with the entrance located along the eastern axis, framed by edges repaired with recent brickwork. Adjacent to the entrance are the remains of a stone protective wall in an “L” shape. The rear façade exhibits even more extensive degradation and visible signs of intervention. Severely deteriorated masonry immediately to the right of the entrance was restored after 2018, resulting in the partial loss of the original wall stratigraphy (Pl. I/2). Surviving elements include a portion of plaster painted white that bears some old scratches, one of which dates back to 1890, as well as a remnant of the building’s original plinth. The northern wall – formerly the northern façade prior to the “Balthes” phase – was reconstructed on its upper floor, leaving only the lower sections with the original plaster painted white and bush-hammered (Pl. V/4).

Inside, the ground floor of the southern wing features two rows of enfilade rooms. In the eastern tract, aligned with the entrance axis, only three compartments survive, though the wall elevations indicate that there were originally four; between P05 and P06, material breaks are evident. The rooms retain the beams of the original ceilings in view. In contrast, the western tract (c. 4.25 m wide) comprises two spaces separated by a masonry wall aligned with the chimney. In both spaces, the vaults with three pairs of penetrations are preserved, but the old plaster survives only in the southwestern space (Pl. I/5, V/1–2).

The second level is accessible directly from the hillside into a rectangular space, the long walls of which still bear traces of a thin brick wall – approximately the width of a single brick – that was removed several years ago. On the left, a similar wall defines room E03. The former subdivision into three spaces explains the presence of three doors leading to the front tract, including E01 and E02 (two rooms corresponding to the vaulted rooms on the ground floor).

At this level, the rooms have flat ceilings, some with exposed beams finished with chamfered corners, while others (eastern rooms) are plastered over a reed-lath support. The degraded plaster exposes traces of interventions, indicating that the dimensions of the spaces in the eastern tract have undergone further modifications over time; originally,

²⁰ Bucur, Balthes [2016]; Rudolf 2021; Foth 2022a.

the tract was subdivided into four compartments aligned with the ground-floor partition walls (Pl. I/5–6). Around the windows and some doors, traces of widening or adaptation to different joinery are evident. Likewise, the stylistic inconsistency of the joinery is indicative of multiple distinct intervention phases. In addition, the degraded floors were removed after 2018, and the northern masonry wall was reconstructed along with a portion of the western side of E02 (to the right of the window).

Above the three-pitched roof of the southern wing, only a single brick chimney remains; a second chimney, located near the junction with the northern wing, has been removed (Pl. I/2–4). The roof slopes still feature small dormer windows with wooden frames along the chimney line. The roof structure preserves part of the original oak framework but now features recent interventions as well. The original section, alongside some beams from the ground- and upper-floor ceilings, provided relevant samples for dendrochronological analysis.²¹

The construction material of this wing is mixed, with varying proportions: Stone predominates in the eastern ground-floor tract; similarly, the masonry of the western rooms up to the exterior stringcourse and the springing of the vaults is mostly stone, while the rest was built primarily with brick, including the moulded cornice with several recesses.

Among the wall finishes, a notable primary layer follows the construction material and is visible to varying degrees on all façades, including the northern façade. This layer consists of lime-and-sand plaster, over which a white-painted surface was systematically hammered. Contemporaneous with this layer are a wide band along the edges of the ground-floor windows and the margin of a former niche between the windows (Pl. II/4); a moulded stringcourse in plaster on a brick support at the transition between the ground floor and the upper floor; and traces of marginal bossages on the main façade, arranged vertically (south and north) (Pl. II/4). All of these elements indicate that at least the main façade was decorated, albeit in a very restrained manner. At the base of the eastern masonry wall, a relief plaster sample suggests that this wing also featured a plinth.

The white-painted, hammered layer is overlaid by another plaster layer, upon which, at the upper floor between the windows, traces of an inscription were scratched. Although barely visible now, it previously read as follows: *ÁG. HITV. EV. NÉPISKOLA / EVANG. VOLKSSCHULE A.B.*²² These two lines, presenting the name of the public school in Hungarian and German, were framed at least once with a polylobed frame – now only faintly discernible – and featured a mirrored vine motif decoration at the lower end (Pl. V/5–6).

The same lime-and-sand plaster covered with white paint was also observed on the interior walls. Additionally, on the west walls of the large rooms on the upper floor, two surfaces with polychrome stencil painting were identified: fragments of two Secession-style friezes – one with roses and buds, the other with an abstract, geometric motif – extending between the window arches and the ceiling-beam level (Pl. V/7–8).

Northern wing

The northern wing also comprises two levels (albeit with different heights) and is in slight projection (ca. 0.65 m) relative to the southern wing. The wing rises on a plan

²¹ Tóth 2024.

²² Rudolf 2021, 157.

measuring 10 × 9.15 m externally, with perimeter walls 0.55–0.60 m thick on the ground floor and 0.50 m thick on the upper floor. The roof is a double-pitched structure oriented east–west; it features trapezoidal gables on the east and west façades as well as brick cornices, either set back in plaster or protected with tiles.

The western façade presents four wide rectangular openings with two different sets of dimensions, contrasting the composition of the southern wing. The northern façade has only a single opening axis on its eastern end: a rectangular ground-floor entrance and a wide, semicircular upper-floor window. To the left of the entrance, there is also a stone protective wall. On the eastern rear side, façade degradation and traces of arches indicate a now-demolished rectangular structure that provided access to the upper floor, its roof intersecting with the trapezoidal gable cornice. At ground level, another entrance with degraded joinery was used to access the upper-floor spaces.

Internally, the floors have now collapsed. In the eastern half, a wooden support structure remains, along with traces of brick masonry reconstructions from recent interventions. On the ground floor, access is available from the northern side through a windfang and a vestibule, leading into a large hall measuring 7.95 × 5.93–6.00 m. Evidence from the upper floor suggests a similar subdivision and northern access. The foundation consists of stone, while the superstructure combines brick and stone or, at the upper level, is built entirely of brick.

The roof structure of the northern wing has lost multiple base elements, with some at the extremities suspended in the air. Only window frames and mullions survive; the remaining components have either disappeared or been stored by the owner. While a few door joineries survive, the floorboards have been lost. Some elements of the rainwater drainage system remain at the corners.

*

Currently, at the Gherdeal school, structural collapses have been halted; however, the roof remains in a problematic state. Events in recent years have affected the building's authenticity, and understanding historical interventions concerning the elevations and the remnants of the original fabric has become a more complex endeavour. This underscores the need to correlate field data with archival survey information (Pl. III). These sources complement an old photograph (already published) showing the school with just a single wing (previously referred to as the “southern wing”), i.e., the pre-Balthes configuration.²³

The pre-Balthes school: the “Angermann” phase

The three buildings that still dominate the centre of the village – the Saxon church with its western tower (surrounded by a fortified enclosure), the school, and the Evangelical parsonage – appear together in a winter photograph by Josef Heinrich Briegel, taken prior to the execution of Balthes' project (1912–1913) (Pl. II/3)²⁴. The school, situated to the left (northwest of the church), is a two-storey building with a hipped roof pierced by a

²³ Fabini 1998, 257.

²⁴ It is possible that J. H. Briegel (1854–1942), a photographer known especially for his work in Sibiu and Făgăraş, took this photograph between 1893 and 1910, during the period when he had his studio in Făgăraş, “opposite the castle gate.” For more on his activity, see Miklósi-Sikes 2001, 105.

central chimney, forming a compact volume. The main (western) façade features four rectangular windows arranged along two widely spaced axes. Several architectural details are discernible: the transition between levels, the plinth, and two vertical rows of marginal bossages at the extremes. On the southern side, at the ground-floor level and at the edge of the slope, a protective wall can also be observed.

Briegel's photograph serves as a valuable visual document, providing a *terminus ante quem* for the elementary school building. Likewise, the topographical survey from 1869–1887 (Pl. II/2) marks a construction northwest of the Saxon church that may correspond to the school. More precise data are derived from older archival surveys and from a 2024 dendrochronological analysis, which will be referred to below.

In the archive preserved at Teutsch House in Sibiu,²⁵ the surveys produced in 1912 for Gherdeal by Balthes' office are held, alongside two older plans (Pl. III/1–2). One, undated, bears the signature of engineer Mathias Joseph Angermann;²⁶ the other, from 1905, is by Johann Guip from Merghindeal²⁷ and was previously mentioned by Gerhild Rudolf.²⁸

Under the title *Plan zu einer neu zu erbauenden Schule in Girtlen* ("Plan for a new school building in Gherdeal"), the first sheet, executed in two tones (grey and pink), features representations of the main façade, ground-floor and upper-floor plans, a roof plan, and a transverse section (Pl. III/1). All elements depict a simple, compact building on a rectangular plan subdivided into six spaces on two levels. The spaces are arranged symmetrically in two groups – north and south – although the drawings do not indicate how they communicate through the central area, which was to house the heating system. On both sides, supporting walls for the sloping terrain are sketched in an "L" shape. The roof, under a four-pitched covering, exhibits an eclectic character. The main façade shows a plinth, lateral bossage decoration, and a stringcourse between levels. No other significant components (e.g., vaults, interior/exterior staircases) are marked on the drawings.

Comparing these sketches with Briegel's photograph and current surveys indicates that this sheet represents the design according to which the pre-Balthes school was constructed. The drawing reveals that the main façade was conceived with three axes, explaining the present spacing between the openings. Between the rectangular windows, each with six panes, there is a central axis with two semicircularly closed niches at the upper ends (Pl. III/1). The upper-floor niche is most likely located beneath the inscription and decoration from the "Balthes" phase, meaning that it is unlikely to be physically recoverable despite it possibly containing elements – inscriptions or decorative features – that would have given the building a more personalised character.

Dendrochronology – done on several relevant samples with numerous growth rings (including some with *Waldkante*) identified in the ceiling beams of the ground floor, upper floor, and roof structure²⁹ – has provided crucial support for dating the school designed by Angermann. These analyses have demonstrated that the last timber felled for the first

²⁵ I.e., "Friedrich Teutsch" Centre for Dialogue and Culture of the Evangelical Church A.C. in Romania (Sibiu)/ Begegnungs- und Kulturzentrum Friedrich Teutsch der Evangelischen Kirche A.B. in Rumänien (Hermannstadt)/ Centrul de Dialog și Cultură „Friedrich Teutsch” al Bisericii Evanghelice C.A. din România.

²⁶ ZAEKR, Gürteln, 604/2916 (old reference: 400/234/260).

²⁷ ZAEKR, Schulhaus Gürteln, 604/2917 (400/234/260).

²⁸ Rudolf 2021, 157.

²⁹ Seventeen samples were collected in total, Tóth 2024.

Tab. 1. Chronological relationship of the wood samples (shaded: sapwood rings; black dot: *Waldkante*) (Anno Domini Dendrolab, Miercurea Ciuc, 2024).

phase of the school dates to the winter of 1850/1851 and the summer of 1851 (Tab. 1). Accordingly, the Angermann-phase school may be dated no earlier than 1851.

It should also be noted that geotechnical surveys of the building's foundations did not indicate any prior construction,³⁰ although Angermann's plan specifies a new school building. Therefore, the possibility of the future identification of an earlier village school that predates the mid-nineteenth-century structure cannot be excluded – potentially even within the fortified church, as has been documented in other cases.

Mathias Joseph Angermann (1808–1880)

The engineer Mathias J. Angermann is scarcely known even within Saxon historiography. He appears in connection with Gherdeal, but not concerning the school – rather, in relation to the church. H. Fabini's atlas credits him as the author of the current two-storey building housing the southwestern entrance to the fortified church in Gherdeal (Pl. V/1).³¹

Angermann was born in Cincu (where his father held the office of royal judge) lived from 1808 to 1880. He studied in Vienna, at the Polytechnic Institute, until 1829 and subsequently worked for several decades in southern Transylvania, primarily in the Cincu district, although he also worked in Braşov before (1830–1836).³² His positions and

³⁰ Barna 2022, 8–12 and oral information provided by Cristinel Plantos.

³¹ Drafted "J. Angermann" (Fabini 1998, 257).

³² Szabó, Szögi 1998, 55; Stenner 1916, 4. I would like to thank my colleague Zsolt Kovács for the discussions and suggestions concerning the biography of this engineer, who was part of the local elite, as well as for his other contributions to the study.

achievements may presently be reconstructed only from scattered references in nineteenth- and twentieth-century publications, although additional archival information likely exists. In 1840, he was appointed the forest master (*Forstmeister*) and district engineer (*Kreis-Ingenieur*) of the Cincu district.³³ Erhard Antoni attributed to him the design of a cemetery chapel – built in the Doric style with four tall wooden columns and rich detailing – constructed in the Cincu in 1842. The same author reported that Angermann also built houses in the area,³⁴ constructed the road between Cincu and Cincșor, and drafted a restoration plan for the fortified church in Bruuiu (which was never implemented).³⁵ One unverified source suggests that the Evangelical church in Făgăraș was built in line with his plans in 1841–1843.³⁶ On several occasions (e.g., 1855, 1872), Angermann (recorded as Máthyás) is also listed as a tax collector.

His projects in Gherdeal – the gatehouse of 1846 and the school of 1851 – provide some guidance regarding Angermann's stylistic approach: sober, symmetrical forms with compact volumes and central axes marked by niches or openings, all combined with restrained decoration. This repertoire includes marginal flat-relief bossages and elongated plaster bands on larger wall surfaces or around windows. Openings may be rectangular or semicircular, with some functioning as skylights, as seen at the Gherdeal gatehouse or the Făgăraș church. Several features – such as the treatment of the centrally located ground-floor entrance with a wide corner recess and semicircular closure, the central-axis niches of the school, and the vaults – suggest that the interior reconstruction of the church within the fortified enclosure in Gherdeal (dated by historiography and the *List of Historical Monuments* to the mid-nineteenth century) may likewise have been based on a project designed by Angermann (Pl. VI). However, such clarifications, which might emerge from the parish archives, remain a task for future research.

The first proposal for school expansion: Johann Guip from Merghindeal, 1905

As revealed by archival research, another proposal for the expansion of the Gherdeal school existed before Fritz Balthes' project. This project was signed by a certain Johann Guip from Merghindeal (an otherwise unknown figure) in 1905, entitled *Bauplan für den Anbau eines Lehrsaales an die ev. Volksschule A–B in Gürtlen* (“Construction Plan for the Extension of a Classroom to the Evangelical Public School A–C in Gherdeal”). This proposal was never executed; however, a minimal comparative analysis proves it to be useful for research, in relation to Angermann's project, today's construction details, and Balthes' project for Gherdeal (Pl. III).

In Guip's drawings, the existing school's ground-floor and upper-floor plans are shown in black, the proposed extension in red, and modifications to the preexisting structure in yellow and blue. These details must be critically assessed and verified during the execution of the new project, as some inaccuracies or omissions are already apparent. For instance, the ground floor does not indicate functions, and the two vaults do not correspond to

³³ *Siebenbürger Wochenblatt*, 4/101 (17.12.1840), 412.

³⁴ A house project from his early years (1826) is held in the National Archives of Hungary (MNL OL, T 75–No. 46/1–2).

³⁵ Antoni 1973, 6. At the time Antoni was writing, the chapel was in ruins.

³⁶ *Die Generalkirchenstation*, 1174; Fabini 1998, 190.

those present today. Conversely, the upper-floor plans note the intended use of each room, suggesting the arrangement of a teacher's residence. Entrances were placed on the east via two staircases connected to a hallway and a larger, rectangular kitchen located centrally in the eastern tract, with specific installations near the building's central chimney. The kitchen would have had two symmetrically placed windows on the east wall, flanking the entrance. The partition wall in the eastern tract, provided in Angermann's plan and aligned with one of the staircases, is not represented in Guip's proposal and may not have ever existed. Moreover, a pantry is indicated to the left of the kitchen.

The two large front rooms would have had only one access point, each from the kitchen, with intercommunication between them; here, two openings are marked that do not appear in Angermann's plan but are visible today, one of which was reused or enlarged by Balthes (Pl. IV/b). The windows of the two western rooms on the upper floor were to be modified to align with the new northern extension (marked in red), corresponding to the classroom (*Lehrsaal*).

In Guip's proposal, the new wing was to have the same width as the original core (9.45 m), a length of 8.48 m, and a masonry height of 6.70 m. It was also to have two levels, the lower with small vaults and the upper with a flat ceiling. Guip did not depict the building's façade (or, at least, such a sketch did not survive), but the plans indicate that the placement of openings in the new wing respected the alternation of axes with niches and windows on the preexisting western façade, designed by Angermann. For the northern extension, Guip proposed a ground-floor entrance and a window on the west side, with a niche and a window above on the upper floor. On the north façade of the extension, two window axes are drawn, while the east side shows solid walls without openings. On the shared southern wall, the proposal includes the infill of one window and the creation of a door connecting the classroom to the hallway in the original building, with access from the hillside (Pl. III/2).

The "Balthes" phase (1912–1913)

Guip's project was never executed; just a few years later, in 1912, the Evangelical community of Gherdeal commissioned Fritz Balthes to transform the preexisting school into a teacher's residence and to construct new spaces to meet the needs of both the school and the community (Pl. III/3).³⁷ At that time, Balthes was also working for two nearby Evangelical communities: in Bruiu, at the school; and in Şomartin, at the community hall. Earlier, he had designed school buildings in Mediaş (1909–1912) and Cincşor (1909–1911).³⁸ As in other cases, he developed his project in Gherdeal within the context of the fortified church and the Saxon parsonage, designing a multifunctional building (Pl. III/3)³⁹ as well as a mixed sanitary installation to serve it (Pl. IV/2).⁴⁰

³⁷ About the contract (now preserved in the Teutsch House archive): Rudolf 2021; Foth 2022a.

³⁸ Lißke 2021, 146.

³⁹ The architectural surveys discussed here were promoted and published already (in selection) by both Rudolf 2021 and Foth 2022b, figs. 144–146.

⁴⁰ To date, we have not identified the location where it was placed. There would, however, have been sufficient space on the plateau east of the school.

The preexisting school was allocated for office space, a cellar (ground floor), and a teacher's residence (upper floor). In his survey – depicted with grey hatching and including more architectural details than the plans of Angermann or Guip – Balthes proposed ground-floor interventions to widen or close five openings (doors to the northwest room and windows on the north side) as well as the infilling of a niche on the main façade. In the eastern tract (noted as *Keller/cellar*), he proposed the partial demolition of the central wall (highlighted in yellow) to create a wider opening, with the rooms arranged in enfilade. Access to the vaulted ground-floor rooms (*Kanzlei*) was to be available only via a single door from the southwest room.

The survey of the upper floor of the preexisting school shows that most of the modifications at this level were proposed by Balthes. Access was arranged at the point indicated by Guip, on the eastern wall, where two windows were to be altered and new joinery was to be installed, including at the entrance. A narrow hallway with thin lateral walls was to be constructed; simultaneously, the previous south and north partitions were to be demolished to make room for a left-side room and a kitchen to the right, the latter with access to a pantry (*Speisekammer*) in the new northern wing (Pl. III/3). In addition to the two existing doors (also marked in Guip's plan), for which no new joinery is indicated in red, a direct passage from the hallway to the northwest room and another between the two western rooms was proposed. The windows on the south and west façades were to be widened and fitted with new joinery in the same style as that designed for doors (see, for example, Pl. IV/1).

For the preexisting core, Balthes designed a northern extension (in red) (Pl. III/3), with dimensions not far from Guip's earlier proposal (8.90 m to the north versus Guip's 8.48 m) but with a taller volume and set approximately 0.50 m in projection relative to the older wing, featuring trapezoidal masonry gables and an east–west roof, surmounted by a small bell tower. Internally, he designed taller rooms (over 4 m, compared with approximately 3 m previously), starting from a floor level lower than that of the original building (Pl. III/3). The ceremonial/community hall, accessible from the eastern axis of the northern façade, was placed on the ground floor. In contrast, the classroom, accessible from the east through a rectangular portico equipped with semicircular arches on the elevation, was located on the western side of the upper floor. In front of it, along the eastern line, were a small hall, a pantry, and a cloakroom.

Balthes' design was executed in 1913, completed within a matter of months. Although the terms of the contract are known, further information regarding the complete execution of the project (e.g., finishes) could be recovered from on-site investigation, ideally during the implementation of the new revitalisation project. Primary research could reveal the original wall colours beyond the currently visible brown tones on large exterior surfaces and will clarify the decorative repertoire employed in the building beyond the fragments that are now difficult to read on the upper-floor façade of the old school (Pl. V/5–6) and in the western upper-floor rooms (Pl. V/7–8).

Final conclusions

Based on the correlation of data from 2023–2024, it can be affirmed that the elementary school predating F. Balthes' intervention was constructed after 1850 in line

with the design of Mathias J. Angermann, the same engineer from the Cincu who had contributed to reconstructions within the fortified church ensemble in Gherdeal as well as other localities (in the Cincu–Făgăraș area, and possibly in Brașov).

The mid-nineteenth-century school building designed by Angermann in Gherdeal was austere, organised on two levels with a compact volume, was built on a rectangular plan, and comprised six spaces on each floor (some vaulted, others with flat ceilings) served by a centrally located heating system. The main façade had three axes: two with rectangular windows and a central axis with semicircularly closed niches, presumably containing inscriptions and/or decorative elements. The wall stratigraphy was simple, consisting of plaster overlaid with whitewash (both interior and exterior). Access to the school building was most likely from the south and north on the ground floor and from the east on the upper floor, as the project did not indicate an interior staircase. The roof structure, under a four-pitched covering, exhibited an eclectic character.

Grey traces (wide bands) along the edges of the ground-floor windows and the former ground-floor niche, the stringcourse between levels (plaster over brick), and evidence of marginal bossage demonstrate that (at least) the main façade was decorated, albeit modestly, using common materials. Further parietal research conducted during the execution phase of the project may recover additional data regarding the finishes from the “Angermann” phase. As for the upper-floor niche, it is now infilled beneath the inscription in capitals, framed by vegetal decoration from the “Balthes” phase.

Surveys of the building’s foundations did not indicate any prior construction for the 1851 school; however, Angermann’s drawings are titled “*Plan zu einer neu zu erbauenden Schule in Girtlen*,” clearly denoting a project for a new school. Therefore, the possibility of an older village school being identified – potentially even within the fortified church – cannot be ruled out for future research.

By around 1900, the Evangelical community of Gherdeal, like many such communities in the region, required not only a school and a teacher’s residence but also a community hall. A more modest school-expansion proposal from 1905 (by Johann Guip), extending just 8.48 m northward and retaining the same width, was never executed. The project was ultimately realised in 1912–1913 in a more modern, elegant, and imposing form through a collaboration with Fritz Balthes.

From the old school, the perimeter and partition walls were preserved along with much of the roof structure (which was integrated with the new northern wing) and some openings. Upper-floor window openings were enlarged, while joinery was largely replaced, and wall finishes were renewed. The exterior acquired a predominantly brown tone, and above an infilled niche at the centre of the old façade, an inscription was placed within a sgraffito frame, now quite faint. Its decorative framing recalls the ornamental frames found on the façades of the community building in Șomartin, a nearby village.

Regarding the period following nationalisation (1948), there are few available records; however, during the execution of the new project, various traces could still be identified. For example, the main façade, repainted in ochre during the Communist period, retains fragments of an inscription rendered in red, now largely faded and partially lost.

Following all of the construction phases presented here, several decades of abandonment followed, resulting in significant losses: the tile roof covering, the bell turret

designed by Balthes – which, as in other cases, gave the building a distinctive character – portions of the roof structure of the new wing, the portico in front of the upper-floor classroom, the floor slabs of the large hall and the upper-floor anteroom, the interior wall between the two wings, and part of the eastern wall (up to 2014). Joinery was damaged; some elements disappeared entirely, while others were removed for conservation.

In 2017, the building was added to Romania's *List of Historical Monuments* (LHM). Thus, between 2018 and 2020, emergency interventions were undertaken by the new owner. These works involved partial reconstructions and consolidation of masonry, which have only recently been documented (Pl. VI/3, c).

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The elementary school in Gherdeal, despite its architecture having undergone numerous alterations, represents a remarkable example of educational architecture among the Saxons in southern Transylvania. Thanks to prior historiography – but above all thanks to data from field surveys, laboratory analyses and archival sources (both visual and written) – its construction phases throughout the most significant years, 1851–1913, as well as contemporary interventions, have been identified.

Bibliography

- Abrudan 2023 I. O. Abrudan, *Din nou despre biserica „Sfântul Nicolae” din Gherdeal (județul Sibiu)*, Studia Universitatis Cibiniensis. Series Historica, 20 (2023), 25–55.
- Antoni 1935 E. Antoni, *Deutsche Bauernkunst in Gürteln*, Siebenbürgische Vierteljahrsschrift, 58/3 (1935), 217–224.
- Antoni 1973 E. Antoni, *Ein vergessenes Baudenkmal*, Neuer Weg, 7610 (25.10.1973).
- Arcanum Maps Arcanum Maps. Country Maps, *Großfürstentum Siebenbürgen (1769–1773) [B IX a 715] – Josephinische Landesaufnahme and Transylvania (1853–1858; 1869–1870) – Franziszeische Landesaufnahme*, Österreichisches Staatsarchiv. Kriegsarchiv, <https://maps.arcanum.com/en/browse/country/>, accessed 22 May 2025.
- Barna 2022 L. Barna, *Studiu geotehnic. Înființare centru cultural-recreativ prin reabilitare și schimbare de destinație din școală în centrul cultural...*, Cluj-Napoca 2022, ms.
- Bucur, Balthes [2016] I. Bucur, H. Balthes, *Fritz Balthes. Un pionier al proiectării contextuale*, Alțâna – Asociația MONUMENTUM [2016].
- Bucur 2019 I. Bucur, *Studiu istoric Biserica Gherdeal, pr. nr. 4*, Sibiu 2019, ms.
- Burnichioiu 2023 I. Burnichioiu, *Biserica evanghelică din Gherdeal, nr. 51, com. Bruuiu, jud. Sibiu, Sb-II-A-B-12321.01. Studiu de parament*, Alba Iulia 2023, ms.
- Costiuc 2017 S. Costiuc, *Dosare de clasare și declasare din anul 2017*, Buletinul Monumentelor Istorice, S.N. (2017), 93.

- Die Generalkirchenstation* *Die Generalkirchenstation im Groß-Schenker Bezirk*, Siebenbürgisch-Deutsches Tageblatt, 2434 (17.12.1881), 1174.
- Fabini 1998 H. Fabini, *Atlas der siebenbürgisch-sächsischen Kirchenburgen und Dorfkirchen*, vol. I, Hermannstadt 1998.
- Foth 2022a Gy. Foth, *Az erdélyi száz év építészeti reform a Jugendstil és a német Werkbund között – Friedrich Balthes és a modern építészet kezdetei az erdélyi százoknál (1909–1914)/ Reforma arhitecturală săsească între Jugendstil și Deutscher Werkbund – Friedrich Balthes și începuturile arhitecturii moderne la sașii din Transilvania (1909–1914)*, Ph.D. thesis, Babeș-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca 2022, 163–165.
- Foth 2022b Gy. Foth, *Friedrich Balthes – attempt to reconstruct the oeuvre of a Transylvanian Saxon artist*, *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai. Historia*, 67 (Special issue) (2022), 87–109. doi: 10.24193/subbhist.2022.spiss.06.
- Gheorghiu 1985 T. O. Gheorghiu, *Arhitectura medievală de apărare din România*, București 1985.
- Lißke 2021 M. Lißke, *Die ehemalige evangelische Volksschule in Kleinschenk*, In: G. Rudolf, H. Fabini (hrsg.), *Architekt Fritz Balthes 1882–1914. Sein Denken und Schaffen als Beitrag zum siebenbürgischen Kulturerbe*, Hermannstadt/Sibiu 2021.
- Miklósi-Sikes 2001 C. Miklósi-Sikes, *Fényképészek és műtermek Erdélyben, 1839–1916. Tanulmány és okmánytár*, Székelyudvarhely 2001.
- Minghiat, Lucescu, Pop 2001–2003 S. Minghiat, C. Lucescu, A. Pop, *Școala latină din Cincu (județul Brașov)*, *Revista Monumentelor Istorice*, LXXVII/1 (2001–2003), 65–75.
- MNL OL, T 75–No. 46/1–2 Magyar Nemzeti Levéltár. Országos Levéltára, Budapest, *Grundriss zu einem bürgereuten Wohngebäude*, T 75–No. 46/1–2, <https://maps.hungaricana.hu/en/MOLTervtar/5043/>, accessed 22 May 2025.
- Nägler 1981 Th. Nägler *Așezarea sașilor în Transilvania*, București 1981.
- Nussbächer, Klima 1985 G. Nussbächer, H. Klima, *Villa (statt Valle) Gertrudis – Gertrudenthal. Aus der Vergangenheit von Gürteln*, *Neuer Weg*, XXXVII/11328 (29.10.1985).
- Rudolf, Fabini 2021 G. Rudolf, H. Fabini (hrsgs.), *Architekt Fritz Balthes 1882–1914. Sein Denken und Schaffen als Beitrag zum siebenbürgischen Kulturerbe*, Hermannstadt 2021.
- Rudolf 2021 G. Rudolf: „Wie die Saat, so die Ernte”. *Der Um- und Neubau der evangelischen Volksschulen in Braller und Gürteln*. In: G. Rudolf, H. Fabini (hrsgs.), *Architekt Fritz Balthes 1882–1914. Sein Denken und Schaffen als Beitrag zum siebenbürgischen Kulturerbe*, Hermannstadt/Sibiu 2021.
- Siebenbürger Wochenblatt* *Siebenbürger Wochenblatt*, Kronstadt, 4/101 (17.12.1840).
- Stenner 1916 F. Stenner, *Die Beamten der Stadt Brassó (Kronstadt) von Anfang der städtischen Verwaltung bis auf die Gegenwart*, Kronstadt 1916.

- Suciu 1967 C. Suciu, *Dicționar istoric al așezărilor din Transilvania*, vol. I, București 1967.
- Szabó 2003 A. M. Szabó, *Erdély, Bánság és Partium történeti és közigazgatási helységnévtára*, vol. I, Csíkszereda 2003.
- Szabó, Szögi 1998 M. Szabó, L. Szögi, *Erdélyi peregrinusok. Erdélyi diákok európai egyetemeken 1701–1849*, Marosvásárhely 1998.
- Tóth 2024 B. Tóth, *Școala ev. din Gherdeal. Analiza dendrocronologică*, Miercurea Ciuc (Anno Domini Dendrolab) 2024, ms.
- ZAEKR Arhiva Centrală a Bisericii Evanghelice C.A. din România, Sibiu / Zentralarchiv der Evangelischen Kirche A.B. in Rumänien, Hermannstadt, Gürteln, Evangelische Volksschule A.B., 604.

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Pl. I. 1. The fortified church in Gherdeal and the Evangelical school (on left) in 1996 (G. Dumitriu, NHI); the school displays a small bell tower (later dismantled); 2–5. The former school building in 2014 (S. Jammer, in Rudolf 2021) and 2024 (I. Burnichioiu); 6–7. Floor plans of the building (ground floor and upper floor) in 2024 (R. Makkos, T. Pavelescu and MODUL 28, Sibiu).

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Pl. II. 1. The village of Gherdeal in the topographical surveys of 1769–1773 and 1869–1887 (Arcanum Maps); **2.** The elementary school before the “Balthes” project, photo by J. H. Briegel from Făgăraș (Fabini 1998, 257); **3–4.** Details of the nineteenth-century school: grey traces of mouldings between the ground floor and the upper floor, of rustication, and of the (walled-in) niche of the ground floor, contemporary with the bush-hammered surfaces of a simple whitewash covering the entire building.

Pl. III. Plans of the school in Gherdeal (1850–1913) (ZAEKR, 604/2900–2017):
 1. Mathias J. Angermann (ca. 1850, built project); 2. Johan(n) Guip (1905, unbuilt project);
 3. Fritz Balthes (1912, built project in 1913).

Pl. IV. 1. Project for a door frame with a transom light at the eastern entrance to the classroom (F. Balthes, ZAEKR, 604/2906); **2.** Details from the sanitary installation project of the school for girls and boys (F. Balthes, ZAEKR, 400/234/260); **3.** The northeastern room of the old school: **a.** blocked opening, indicated in Guip's plan (Pl. III/2); **b.** door frames from the "Balthes" phase in the interior of the old school (photo by I. Burnichioiu, 2023); **c.** door frame before the "Balthes" phase.

Pl. V. 1–2. Vaulted rooms on the ground floor of the old school; 3. Southwestern room of the old school with a ceiling of hewn beams chamfered at the corners; 4. Brick masonry with multiple interventions between the old school and the “Balthes” phase; 5–6. Traces of the inscription in plaster on the main façade (photo by L. Kiss, 2022); 7–8. Fragments of frieze decorations, Secession style, in the southwestern and northwestern rooms of the upper floor (beneath wood beam dated ca. 1850) (photo by Anno Domini Dendrolab, 2024).

Pl. VI. 1. Plan of the fortified church of Gherdeal (Ioan Bucur) and the southwestern gatehouse to which Mathias J. Angermann contributed in 1846; **2.** The Evangelical church of Făgăraș, attributed to Mathias J. Angermann, probably 1841–1843 (photo by M. R. Țetcu, 2019); **3.** Plan of the construction stages of the school in Gherdeal (1851–2020).